

Mentoring function implementation in the personalised learning environment of the OSCAR project

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For OSCAR we designed and implemented the first version of the *mentoring* service on our open, personalised learning platform, powered by Artificial Intelligence (AI). The platform is available on <http://edoer.eu/> after a quick registration. In this version, at any moment, users can request for mentoring by selecting the area (which can be any of the skills or learning topics in the system) they need help on and providing a brief explanation of their problem. Afterward, the request is sent to the experts in the selected area, and will be assigned to the first expert who accepts the request. When an expert accepts a request, he/she is able to access the mentee’s contact information and start the mentoring process. Finally, when the mentoring process is finished, the mentor can close the request. The following figure shows the current mentoring process on our platform.

In the following sections, we will explain each of the mentioned steps in more detail and afterward discuss the technologies we have used to implement this service.

Creating a mentioning request

At any page, users can press on the *help* button and request for mentoring. On the request page, users can search through all the existing skills and learning topics in the system, and set the subject that they need help with. Also, they can describe their problem in a few words. The following picture is a screenshot from the request mentoring page.

I need a mentor

What do you need help with? *

Stress management

Explain Briefly (optional)

I am full of stress and I don't know what to do.

CANCEL REQUEST

Assigning mentoring requests to mentors

After submitting the mentoring request, all mentors, who are experts in the target area (i.e. the area that the mentee has requested help for), can display the request and decide whether to accept or reject it. The mentors can visit all the related requests (i.e. as eligible requests) on their dashboard, as shown in the following picture, and each request will be assigned to the first expert who accepts it.

Eligible Requests

Requester	On	Request Date	Request Text	Your decision?
Reza Tavakoli	Stress management	2021-12-22 16:13:31	I am full of stress and I don't need what to do.	ACCEPT REJECT
Mark Eli	Stress management	2021-11-10 10:24:19		ACCEPT REJECT

Rows per page: 10 1-2 of 2 < >

Processing a request by a mentor

If a mentor decides to accept a request, the request will be moved to the “Active Requests” part. Mentors can find the contact information of their mentees, and brief information about their requests on their active request dashboard. After finishing the mentoring process, mentors can close the request.

The screenshot shows the eDoer web interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with 'eDoer' logo, 'GOALS', 'LEARN', and 'EXAMS' buttons, a search bar, and a user profile for 'REZA TAVAKC'. The main content area is titled 'Mentoring Requests' with the subtitle 'Watch your active and eligible requests'. Below this is a section for 'Active Requests' containing a table with one row of data.

Requester	On	Accepting...	Request Text	Contact	Close Request
Reza Tavakoli	Stress management	2021-12-22 16:15:44	I am full of stress and I don't need ...	mohamadreza.tavakoli1989@gmail...	CLOSE REQUEST

At the bottom right of the table, there is a pagination control showing 'Rows per page: 10' and '1-1 of 1'.

Technologies we have used

To implement the mentoring service which is available on eDoer.eu, we needed to implement a backend and a frontend part. To implement the backend part, we used Django version 3.2.4 and Django-REST-framework version 3.12.4. The backend implementations are available on [Gitlab](#). Also, ReactJS version 17.0.2 was used to implement the frontend parts which are again available on [Gitlab](#). It should be mentioned that the Gitlab repositories are private at the moment, and when the projects get stable, we will make them public. In case you want to get access to the repositories, please send us your request through Gitlab or email.